

HISTORY OF TOURISM

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In this contemporary world, tourism is becoming a large business which plays a key role in the economy of many developed and developing countries. It offers great opportunities especially for developing parts of the globe and emerging economies. Tourism creates a number of job opportunities for the residents of the countries, strengthens the local economy, contributes to local infrastructure development and can help to conserve the natural environment and cultural assets and traditions, and to reduce poverty and inequality. The number of jobs created by tourism in many different areas is significant. These jobs are not only a part of the tourism sector but may also include the agricultural sector, communication sector, health sector, and the educational sector. Many tourists travel to experience the hosting destination's culture, different traditions and the gastronomy. This is very profitable to local restaurants, shopping centres, and stores. But do you know when did tourism appear?

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Although today we take it for granted that we travel around the world to admire the monuments and landmarks of the past. We prepare for such trips by reading about what we are going to see, set out in the journey with a good idea of how we will get there and where we will stay and have a sense of what we will encounter on location. Cyriacus Ancona, the first cultural tourist since antiquity, lacked these advantages when, in the first half of the 15th century, he sailed around the Mediterranean in a search of the remains of Greek and Roman civilisations.

Cyriacus first became fascinated by ancient monuments while walking in his home city Ancona and looking at the marble arch, erected in AD 115, to the Roman Emperor Trajan. He suddenly saw the structure in a new light. He no longer saw it as just a familiar and generally overlooked landmark, but as a doorway to the wonders of ancient imperial Rome. Not many people of Cyriacus's time were interested in historical travel, they generally ignored old buildings and structures, or worse, dismantled them for their building materials.

Cyriacus decided to see the world himself and to record details of whatever other antiquities remained to be discovered. His training as a merchant did not prepare him for this vacation; he did not ancient languages, history or art. However, he set out to solve these failings, first by learning Latin at the age of 30 and then adding ancient Greek. Having done this, he then set off on voyages around the Mediterranean to find, investigate and understand ancient cultures from their buildings, sculptures and inscriptions. Thus, he became the first archeological and cultural tourist, predating other antiquarians by some 200 years

Travel in the 15th century, however, was anything but simple or enjoyable. Overland journeys by foot or mule along bad roads, under constant threat from bandits, were bad; voyages by sea were even worse. When the weather cooperated, sailing went relatively smoothly, ships proceeded along coasts from one recognizable landmark to another. However, when there was no wind the ship did not move. Strong winds were no friends either, they drenched the ship with lashing waves and blew it off course. Water swamped the deck, splashed into the cabins and soaked mattresses, clothes and food. Remarkably, Cyriacus never complained about the miseries of travel. Optimistic by nature, he endured such hardships unafraid and saw opportunities where other people saw setbacks.

Among many of the important records made by Cyriacus was his crucial documenting, in 1431, of the remains of the Cyzicus, an ancient Roman city that had relied on commerce for its financial success. He hired a local person to take him to site and then had to work out for himself the significance of the ruins he was looking at because there was no guidebook on ancient architecture to help him. Indeed, his contemporary knowledge about the ruins. Cyzicus had been a splendid city in its prime. Unfortunately, the area was highly seismic and in AD 123 the city was so devastated by a major earthquake that, when the Roman Emperor Hadrian visited it the following year, he was so saddened that he decided to subsidize a campaign to reconstruct Cyzicus. He made a substantial donation for anew temple to the Roman go Yupiter. Cyriacus thought the ruining city was awe-inspiring. He found the remains of the temple and examined it in great detail, looking for clues in ancient texts to help him understand what he was seeing. He sketched the great doorway adorned with carved foliage and mythological characters. Cyriacu's account of this temple is the only record of this building as in the following centuries it was entirely stripped of all its stonework and all that remained is its base.

Cyriacus also visited mainland Greece, in 1436, when no one went to Greece in order to see the country's ancient ruins. One of his destinations was the sanctuary of Delphi. The ancient Greeks considered Delphi as being situated in the most beautiful spot in Greece. When Cyriacus arrived at the site of Delphi, however, he found war, earthquakes and avalanches had all but obliterated its ruins. Determined to find any ancient traces, Cyriacus spent six days walking all over the areas, peering at odd stone blocks sticking out of the ground, running his hands over inscriptions to trace fragments of words, and trying to puzzle out the few surviving structural remains. Climbing uphill towards the rocks that tower over the site, he came upon a theatre built into the slope. Soon after his visit, the site was buried by a rockslide and was not seen again until archeologists began to excavate the area systematically in the late 19th century.

Cyriacus had hoped to visit Egypt and Ethiopia but he never got there. However, in his life he did record for posterity countless ancient monuments around the Mediterranean, paving the way for future archeologists and cultural tourists.

A Silesian gentleman, Hentzner by name, who acted as traveling tutor in the last year of the sixteenth century, acknowledges that the troubles of a traveler are great, and finds only two arguments to countervail them; first, that man is born unto trouble; and secondly, that Abraham had orders to travel direct from God. Abraham, however, did not have to cross the channel. Otherwise, perhaps, the prospect of sacrificing himself, as well as his only son Isaac, would have brought to light a flaw in his obedience. There was, it is true, the chance of crossing from Dover to Calais in four hours three hundred years ago, but in 1610 two ambassadors waited at Calais fourteen days before they could make a start; and making a start by no means implied arriving— at least, not at Dover. One gentleman, after a most unhappy night, found himself at Nieuport next morning, and had to wait three days before another try could be made. Yet another, who had already sailed from Boulogne after waiting six hours for the tide, accomplished two leagues; and being becalmed for nine or ten hours, returned to Boulogne by rowing-boat, and posted to Dover on Monday between four and five in the morning. It was naturally a rare occurrence to go the whole distance by small boat, because of the risk. Lord Herbert of Cherbury was the most noteworthy exception. The noble lord made three attempts from Brill, and covered distances varying from a point just outside the harbor to halfway, but each time arrived at Brill again. eventually, he went by land to Calais, where the sea was so dangerous that no one would venture- no one except one old

freshman, whose boat, as he himself acknowledged, was one of the worst in the harbor, but who, on the other hand, did not mind whether he lived or died.

Increasing the socio-economic effects caused by the tourism development in the local population, they adopt some attitudes according to the impacts directly or indirectly perceived. However, some of this impact can be considered positive or negative, according to the different perspectives. The issue of the resident-tourist relationship has been much discussed recently. Therefore, many case studies are being conducted that address the impacts on both residents and tourists. The goal of this manuscript is to analyze the attitudes of local residents to the development of tourism in the urban monument zones. Primary data was collected in a questionnaire survey for residents who have a permanent residence.

The apex of European tourism began in the 1960s: in response to the economic situation and strategic innovations in the market economy, commercial tour operators and travel companies transformed the nature of competition through increasingly cheaper offers, propelling it in the direction of mass tourism, introducing new destinations and modes of holidaying. Here, tourism producing its own structures and secondary systems. Many travel agencies and tourist organizations were set up, while department stores also offered package holidays, for example, Neckermann in Germany from 1963s and Jelmoli in Switzerland from 1972s. The replacement of bus and rail travel with journeys by car and caravan, and later by air, provided a powerful stimulus. Charter tourism occupied a flourishing market sector and established itself with cheap offerings for foreign holidays. Foreign tourism first affected neighboring countries and then more distant destinations- Austria and Switzerland were popular among German holidaymakers, but Italy and Spain later gained increasing prominence: from about 1970, journeys abroad clearly represented the majority; this trend towards foreign holidays has recently grown even stronger. In general, the number of teenagers and adults taking foreign holidays rose more than threefold over the 40 years before 1991 – from nine to 32 million.

Nowadays, tourism represents a substantial and fast-growing sector of the economy of Uzbekistan. The government of Uzbekistan under President Shavkat Mirziyoyev has invested heavily in developing tourism as a high-growth potential industry, resulting in an increase in international arrivals from approximately 1 million in 2016 to 7 million in 2023.

Uzbekistan's most-visited tourist sites are associated with the history of the Silk Road, particularly the cities of Bukhara, Khiva and Samarkand. The Registan ensemble in Samarkand, a complex of three madrasahs dating from the 15-17th centuries situated around the city's historic central square, is one of Uzbekistan's most-visited landmarks attracting more than 1million visitors in 2022. The government of Uzbekistan continues to invest in both developing tourism-related infrastructure, and marketing Uzbekistan as a tourism destination.

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